

SOCIAL SCIENCIES

ETHICAL CONCERNS OF USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN JOURNALISM: QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS (CASE OF GEORGIA)

Dali Osepashvili

*Dr. Prof. of Journalism and Mass Communications
International Black Sea University, Georgia
ORCID: 0000-0003-2192-2760*

Abstract

The goal of the paper is to show the results of the study on how Georgian media professionals assess the ethical challenges associated with the use of artificial intelligence in journalism and what threats they see in this regard.

The semi-structured interviews-method was used for this purpose. The study was conducted from February 1 till 20 April 2025. At the whole 10 media professionals (journalists and representatives from academia) participated in this qualitative study.

Although the active use of artificial intelligence in Georgian journalism has not yet begun, most media professionals have a skeptical attitude. They discuss ethical challenges as the main threat.

According to this study, the main concerns are copyright, plagiarism-related challenges, lack of regulations and fears related to personal data. Most of the questioned respondents believe that artificial intelligence tools can only be used by journalists as auxiliary tools for creating content.

As they noted, despite the ethical challenges, they will have to accept and incorporate this innovation, because the journalism of the future will inevitably be without artificial intelligence.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence and Journalism; Ethical Concerns & AI; Georgian Media

Introduction

AI, as the latest technological innovation for media, is quickly being established in newsrooms and has become increasingly integral part of journalistic practice. However, despite positive aspects, its use also poses challenges in terms of journalistic ethics.

In recent years, since the emergence of ChatGPT from early 2022, a number of concerns and worries arise regarding the ethical aspects of using AI (Barceló-Ugarte, T. et al. Gutierrez-Caneda, B. et al., 2024; Forja-Pena, T., García-Orosa, B., & López-García, X. (2024); Kalfeli, P & Angel, C. 2025); etc.

This study is based on journalism ethic as a theoretical framework. The purpose of this paper is to show the results of the study on how Georgian media professionals assess the ethical challenges associated with the use of artificial intelligence in journalism and what threats they see in this regard. Although the active use of artificial intelligence in Georgian journalism has not yet begun, most media professionals have a skeptical attitude.

Main research Questions

RQ1. What are the main challenges for newsrooms while using of AI from the ethical point of view?

RQ2. What ethical aspects should be considered in the process of integrating artificial intelligence tools into journalistic routines?

Literature Review

A number of concerns and worries arise in the studies, regarding of the using AI in journalism and ethical aspects.

As Barceló-Ugato and her co-authors emphasized, AI has recently become notable in the field of communications and journalism and they provide in their study "...conceptual framework to the relationship between

AI and journalistic ethics" (Barceló-Ugato, T., et. al. 2021).

According to Encyclopedia of Business and Professional Ethics, journalism ethic: "Today, this concept is more than ever threatened. With the advent of artificial intelligence applications and the use of digital data in journalism, the nature of how news is selected, produced, distributed, and consumed is changing" (Dorr, K., 2023., p. 138).

Pavlik consider question of accountability as the main ethical issues, "...because generative AI systems are capable of creating new content, such as text, audio, or images, there is a concern that they could be used to produce misleading or malicious information that is difficult for humans to distinguish from genuine content. This could lead to the spread of fake news and other harmful information, which could have serious consequences for individuals and society as a whole" (Pavlik, JV., 2023, p. 88).

According to Reynolds and Nolan, AI technology provides new options for news production and distribution, but also raises ethical concerns that demand careful consideration and preemptive steps. Their study provides insights for journalists, news organizations, and technology developers to navigate the ethical terrain of AI journalism ethically, while adhering to ideals of fairness, openness, and accountability (Reynolds, S., & Nolan, N. 2023).

The results of the research Al-Zoubi and co-authors concluded that "the main ethical challenges faced by journalists in the newsroom in adopting AI are data bias; privacy violations; and the absence of legislation and international regulations regarding the use of AI in journalism" (Al-Zoubi, O., et. al. 2024. p.401).

According to results of study Gutierrez-Ganeda and co-authors, "...while AI integration offers new opportunities in journalism, it also raises ethical concerns around data privacy, algorithmic biases, transparency, and potential job displacement" (Gutierrez-Ganeda, B., 2024, p. 1).

Spanish researchers Parratt-Fernandez and her co-authors in their study identified "A total of forty ethical codes and guidelines on the use of AI in newsrooms developed and published by news organizations around the world" (Parratt-Fernandez, S., 2024, p.10).

According to another Spanish study the ethical revolution, identified 10 ethical challenges of AI and newsrooms: ethics; transparency in newsrooms; algorithmic transparency; algorithmic bias; data privacy and surveillance; editorial responsibility; copyright; misinformation; equitable access to information; supervision and human intervention (Foria-Pena, T., et. al. 2024).

Diakopoulos and co-authors consider in his quantitative study 11 ethical challenges: no human supervision; inaccurate info; bias; reducing quality; job displacement; lack of transparency; accountability; plagiarism; copyright issues; originality; privacy and data protection (Diakopoulos, N. et. al. 2024).

Porlezza and Shapals in their essay critically evaluated the way news media organizations tackle many ethical challenges related to use of AI systems in entire news cycle (Porlezza, C., & Shapals, A., 2024).

Canadian researchers in their study explores how Canadian journalists are using artificial intelligence and if ethical frameworks are keeping up with technological advancements (Misri. A., et. al, 2025).

Ogheneruona and her co-authors highlight their study as key recommendations, following: "include requiring mandatory disclosure of AI involvement in content production, conducting regular audits to identify and address algorithmic biases, and preserving human editorial judgment as a cornerstone of news production" (Ogheneruona, M., et. al. 2025, p.30).

Kalfeli and Angel explored their study the extent to which artificial intelligence tools are used by Greek journalists and examining benefits, risks and ethical challenges (Kalfeli, P., & Angeli, Ch., 2025).

In Georgia, studies on the ethical aspects of using AI in journalism have not yet been conducted. Moreover, there are no studies on media and artificial intelligence. This highlights the novelty, relevance and actuality of this research.

Method

The data for this explanatory study were collected by qualitative approach. The semi-structured interviews-method was used for this purpose. The study was conducted from February 1 till 20 April 2025.

At the whole 10 Georgian media professionals (journalists and representatives from academia) participated in this qualitative study.

As for the selection, purposive sampling was used. All ten participants are representatives of universities, different media schools but 5 of them are also practicing media professionals from television, radio, or online platforms.

Main Results

As the research revealed, the introduction of artificial intelligence poses a number of challenges for the media. The questioned respondents identified some ethical challenges associated with the use AI in newsrooms.

The first concerns which was emphasized by most of the interviewee was **copyright** and **plagiarism**.

"I think copyright is a main challenge for media, intellectual property must be protected. We should not allow the copy-paste that is being offered to us by AI in the seconds. Sources must be cited and attribution must be made. If this is not done, it will be plagiarism" (one of the respondents).

"It should be clearly stated when AI is used. Using of the blind copying material created by AI, is unacceptable. It is essential that humans are involved in the editing and generation process." (one of the respondents).

"When material is partially or fully produced by AI, readers/viewers are often not informed about this. I am a journalist at Radio Liberty, and on our online platform, we always provide viewers with information about where AI has been used in the content we publish. However, I am not sure that all online media outlets do this. This is a serious challenge" (one of the respondents).

As the study participants pointed out, **accuracy** and **reliability** are also a challenge, as AI-generated content cannot be spread without verification and they emphasized that the human factor is essential here.

"Accuracy is of utmost importance. We need to pay close attention to every word and detail it provides. Even though AI is getting better and better every day, we still need to focus on accuracy."

"Accuracy, specific information needs to be verified, even though artificial intelligence is updated periodically, it may have information, for example, until April and not know what happened after that. Accordingly, it may give us an incomplete text or mislead us."

"For the readers of our magazine, I decided to introduce May Musk one day. A person who fights age stereotypes is an inspiration to many women. That's why I wanted to introduce her memorable quotes to the audience. I asked AI for help. It wrote down a lot of quotes, although I recognized a few and realized that these quotes did not belong to her. Indeed, despite the fact that I clearly told to AI that I was looking for May Musk's quotes, it wrote down Elon Musk's quotes... If I hadn't checked, Elon's words would have been attributed to May Musk" (one of the respondents).

As some participants noted, the problem of spreading **disinformation**, as well as the use of manipulative methods, is no less of a challenge.

"From an audio-visual perspective, we see that the technical side of creating so-called fake visuals is slowly improving and it is becoming almost impossible to distinguish them. (one of the respondents).

"It is possible to fake a lot of things. Some online media can make ChatGPT a respondent and say that they interviewed someone." (one of the respondents).

One respondent also mentioned the problem of **algorithmic bias** among the ethical challenges.

"There is also algorithmic bias, and we need to be aware of this challenge as well – AI tools can contain biased content, which affects the perception and analysis of information." (one of the respondents).

Some of the participants named fears of **privacy and personal data** as one of the ethical challenges while using AI.

"It's really useful to use it in the newsroom, because it can help you find information quickly, but isn't personal data at risk? Personally, I'm thinking about it and trying to log in without an account" (one of the respondents).

"I fear that AI often collects large amounts of personal information from users, which may grossly violate ethical standards and privacy principles." (one of the respondents).

As for the question of what ethical aspects should be taken into account in the process of integrating artificial intelligence tools into journalistic routines, and if there are any types of regulations needed for media outlets that would regulate the use of AI from an ethical perspective. Most of the participants think that there is no need for regulations at this stage. It would be too early to talk about it.

I think it would be better to create certain ethical norms that would be available to media outlets.

For example, if the information provided by AI turns out to be false, who is responsible for this? - This should be determined by the internal code of ethics. If the audience feels that media materials are created "automatically", superficially and without human intervention, they may lose trust in the media - that is, a limit should be set, a dose that does not completely exclude the journalist from the journalistic product.

I think internal ethical codes should be revised to take into account/understand the capabilities and risks of AI. For example, how do we indicate that the source is AI, what notation or annotation do we use? I think that material generated by AI should ultimately be checked by a human. The editorial staff should know what information journalists are or are not providing to AI in order to prevent the spread of confidential information".

Conclusions and limit of the study

According to this study, for Georgian journalists the main concerns about using AI in newsrooms are copyright, plagiarism-related challenges; lack of regulations and fears related to personal data; accuracy and reliability which requires involvement of human factor.

Most of the questioned respondents believe that artificial intelligence tools can only be used by journalists as auxiliary tools for creating content.

As the study revealed, despite the ethical challenges, they newsrooms will have to accept and incorporate this innovation, because the journalism of the future will inevitably be without AI.

This research was limited only ethical concerns of using AI in news journalism and was based on small sample but for further studies it will be interesting to

focus of analyze strengths and opportunities of development. It would also be interesting to conduct comparative research using the examples of other countries.

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